

RESISTANCE TO TRANSVERSE TENSION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL
COMMINGLED CF/PEEK COMPOSITE

Hogyu Yoon, Kiyohisa Takahashi

Department of Materials Science and Engineering
Nagoya Institute of Technology
Gokiso-cho, Showa-ku, Nagoya 466, Japan.

and Kunio Tanakamaru

SIKIBO Ltd., Central Research Laboratory, 1500-5,
Shibahara Minami, Yokaichi-city, Shiga 527, Japan.

ABSTRACT

Resistance to transverse tension of the unidirectional carbon fiber/PEEK composites were examined by uniaxial tensile and cleavage tests. Three types of unidirectional CF/PEEK composites were fabricated from : (a) prepreg sheet, (b) plain weave cloth ; warp : commingled yarn(1800d) of carbon fiber with PEEK fiber, weft : PEEK yarn(70d), (c) 5-shaft sateen weave cloth, warp : carbon yarn(1800d), weft : PEEK yarn(900d). The initial Young's modulus and the breaking strength measured by the transverse tensile tests were the highest on the specimen (a). Those of the specimen (c) were the lowest because of the lack of the CF/PEEK interfacial adhesion. On the other hand, the mode I intralaminar fracture toughness estimated from the cleavage test was the highest on the specimen (b). The interfacial adhesion between the carbon fiber and PEEK resin was also investigated by the SEM observation of the fractured surface after the transverse tension. On specimen (b), the fracture surface was rough and irregular and the fibers were twisted. While, the fracture surface of specimen (a) was flat and smooth and the fibers were parallel to each other. It was concluded that the undulation and twist of the carbon fibers enhanced the fracture toughness of specimen (b).

KEY WORDS: Carbon fiber/PEEK ; Commingled Yarn ; Transverse Tension ;
Intralaminar Fracture Toughness ; SEM Observation

1. INTRODUCTION

In the application of advanced polymeric composites, PEEK (poly (ether-etherketone), a semicrystalline thermoplastic) offers a number of significant advantages over the conventional thermosetting polymers such as epoxy. CF/PEEK composites have attracted much attention in many applications[1-3], because their fracture toughness, heat-resistance, moisture-resistance and storage stability are outstanding compared with those of CF/epoxy composites. Many works have been done to characterize the toughness of neat PEEK and CF/PEEK composites[3-6]. However, there are several difficulties on the fabrication of PEEK composites because of the high melting point of PEEK. In order to help for the melted PEEK to impregnate into the carbon fibers and to disperse homogeneously in the composite, the fabrication method using the commingled yarn instead of the prepreg has been investigated[7]. The commingled yarns of carbon fibers with PEEK filaments have the advantage that they can be applied to the fabrication of 3-dimensional structural composites[8] by weaving or braiding technique.

In this paper, the unidirectional composites are manufactured with the commingled yarns and the cowoven cloths composed of carbon fibers and PEEK filaments. Transverse tensile properties and transverse fracture toughness are measured and compared with composites made of the CF/PEEK and the CF/epoxy prepregs. The adhesion of fiber/matrix interface and the impregnation of PEEK resin into the carbon fibers are also investigated by SEM observations.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials Unidirectional CF/epoxy composites were made from the prepreg ; P25XC/ T300 (Nippon Petrochemicals Co.). Unidirectional CF/PEEK composites were also made from three types of the following base materials.

(a) Prepreg : The unidirectional CF/PEEK prepreg ; APC-2 (Imperial Chemical Industries, ICI). The volume fraction of carbon fiber was 62%.

(b) Commingled : The plain weave cloth (Fig. 1) composed of the warp of commingled yarn(1800d, Schappe Co., France) and the weft of PEEK yarn (70d, Teijin Co.). The commingled yarn is composed of the carbon fiber and PEEK fiber. The carbon and

PEEK filaments are cut by the stretch-breaking method in the length of about 12cm. These staples of 12cm in length are spun to form the commingled yarn. Fig. 2 is a magnification of the commingled yarn, in which the thicker fibers are PEEK and the thinner fibers are carbon. The PEEK fibers melt during hot pressing process to form the matrix. Tips of carbon fiber protrude from the yarn as fluffs. Due to the presence of these fluffs, an improvement of fracture toughness is expected. The fiber volume fraction of the commingled yarn was 52.9%, while that of the plain weave cloth was 49.8%.

(c) Cowoven cloth : A 5-shaft sateen weave cloth(Fig.3) composed of the warp of continuous carbon fiber yarns(diameter $7\mu\text{m} \times 3000$ filaments : 1800d, Toho Beslon Co.) and the weft of PEEK yarn(900d, Teijin Co.). In this cowoven cloth, one side(the face shown in Fig.3) has the higher proportion of carbon fibers than PEEK, while the other side(the hidden side of Fig.3) is PEEK-rich. The volume fraction of carbon fiber in the cowoven cloth was 67%.

2.2 Preparation of specimens Thickness of each specimen after the hot pressing was set to be 1mm. CF/epoxy composites were laminated in the same manner as CF/PEEK prepreg. In the case of cowoven cloth, a PEEK sheet ($25\mu\text{m}$ thickness, Sumitomo Bakelite Co.) was stacked on the surface of the carbon-rich side.

The CF/PEEK composites laminated were inserted between the steel plates on which the mold release agent (Free Coat 44, Hiraizumi Yoko Co.) was coated. They were pressed in a vacuum bag made of polyimide (Upirex, Ube Kosan Co.) at 200°C . The temperature was elevated up to 400°C at a rate of $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ under the same pressure. For preventing oxidation, N_2 gas was introduced into the vacuum bag. The temperature was lowered to about 100°C by natural cooling(about $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) to give the final specimens.

In the case of specimens ; (a) prepreg and (c) cowoven cloth, the pressure was kept at $6\text{kg}/\text{cm}^2$ up to 400°C , and then decreased to $2\text{kg}/\text{cm}^2$ on cooling. In the case of the commingled specimen (b), the pressure was kept at $20\text{kg}/\text{cm}^2$ up to 400°C , and then decreased to $16\text{kg}/\text{cm}^2$ on cooling. Under the lower pressure, the commingled specimen tended to generate voids and it was difficult to obtain a homogeneous specimen. In the case of CF/epoxy prepreg materials, following the precure at 120°C for 45min, they were hot pressed under $20\text{kg}/\text{cm}^2$ at 180°C for 2h to give the final specimens.

2.3 Measurement

2.3.1 Tensile test Transverse tensile tests of the unidirectional carbon fiber

composites were carried out at a constant temperature(30°C). The tensile speed was 1mm/min. The dimensions of the specimens were ; 150mm in length(transverse direction to the fiber), 10mm in width (the fiber direction) and 1mm in thickness.

2.3.2 Cleavage test The specimen as shown in Fig. 4 was employed in order to estimate the intralaminar fracture toughness. The tensile load was applied to the specimen through the chuck perpendicularly to the fiber direction. Tensile speed was 0.5mm/min. When the crack began to propagate and the load lowered, the operator stopped the machine and allowed the crack to self-arrest. Then, the operator marked the new crack tip, unloaded the machine to zero load and measured the new crack length. This procedure was repeated and the fracture toughness was estimated from a measured load-displacement curve.

3. STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE

When a crack is propagating in an elastic body under external force, a constant energy is released to form the new surface. This energy per unit area is called strain energy release rate, G_I . The values of G_I is determined from

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{\partial C}{\partial \bar{a}} \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load, b is the specimen's thickness, C is the compliance, and \bar{a} is the crack length. From the measured P- δ curves(δ is the load-point displacement), the compliance C can be obtained and plotted against the crack length \bar{a} . Using the values of $\partial C/\partial \bar{a}$ obtained from C- \bar{a} curve, G_I can be calculated by eq.(1). In this experiments, the relation between C and \bar{a} was approximated by ;

$$C = R \bar{a}^n \quad (2)$$

where R and n are constants experimentally determined.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Tensile test Comparing the three CF/PEEK composites in Fig. 5, the initial Young's modulus and breaking strength are the highest on the prepreg specimen, and are the lowest on the cowoven cloth specimen. The elongation at break of the cowoven cloth is significantly low. The dotted line is the stress-strain curve of neat PEEK, which yields at stress of 100MPa and strain of about 5%, and breaks at 90MPa and 20%, respectively.

In Fig. 6, the transverse tensile modulus measured are compared with theoretical predictions based on the perfect adhesion, interfacial slippage[9] and cavity formation[10] models at the fiber/matrix interface. The Young's moduli of the prepreg and commingled composites are in good agreement with the theoretical values assumed the perfect adhesion, and those of the cowoven composites with the interfacial slippage model. Therefore, it can be supposed that good interfacial adhesion between the fiber and matrix is obtained in the prepreg and the commingled composites.

4.2 Fracture toughness Fig. 7 shows the dependence of the critical strain energy release rate, G_{IC} , on the crack length. The G_{IC} value seems to be independent of the crack length. The CF/PEEK commingled specimen has a higher value of G_{IC} than the prepreg composite, while the epoxy composite has the lowest value.

It is known that a brittle fracture material which has the higher Young's modulus and the higher breaking strength exhibits the higher fracture toughness. In the present study, the value of fracture toughness of the CF/PEEK commingled specimen was higher than that of the CF/PEEK prepreg specimen, although the commingled specimen showed the lower breaking strength and lower Young's modulus than the prepreg specimen. It may be due to the carbon fiber arrangement in each base material.

4.3 SEM observations The scanning electron microscopic(SEM) observation was conducted on the fracture surfaces of the individual specimen. Fig. 8 shows the fracture surface of the CF/PEEK prepreg specimen. From the fact that the surfaces of the fibers are covered with PEEK resin, which deformed plastically, it is supposed that the impregnation of PEEK resin into the carbon filaments and the adhesion between them are excellent. Therefore, such high breaking stress and Young's modulus as shown in Fig.5 are obtained. The appearance of the fracture surface is uniform independently of the location, and the fibers arrange parallel to each other.

The carbon fibers in the fracture surface of the CF/PEEK commingled specimen are also well covered with PEEK resin, as shown in Fig. 9(a). However, the fracture surface is rough and irregular(Fig. 9(b)), so that the area of fracture surface becomes large. And it may be recognized that the straight propagation of the crack will be arrested. For this reason, it was considered that the fracture toughness was remarkably enhanced although the initial Young's modulus and the breaking strength of the commingled composite were lower than those of the prepreg composite.

For the CF/PEEK cowoven cloth specimen, in which a warp yarn is composed of 3000 filaments of carbon fibers, it is expected that the melted PEEK resin(weft) is difficult to impregnate into the carbon filaments. Consequently, the portion of carbon-rich or PEEK-rich was observed(Fig. 10). The poor interfacial adhesion between carbon fibers and PEEK resin results in the inferior fracture toughness.

Fracture surface of the CF/epoxy prepreg specimen is shown in Fig. 11. Carbon fibers are arranged parallel to each other and the epoxy resin is well impregnated into carbon filaments. However the epoxy resin fractured in a brittle manner, while PEEK resin deformed plastically in a CF/PEEK prepreg specimen (Fig.8).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The effect of the base material on the resistance to transverse tension of unidirectional carbon fiber/PEEK composites was investigated. The prepreg specimen showed the highest values of initial Young's modulus and breaking strength, while the commingled specimen exhibited the highest fracture toughness. Micrographs of the fracture surface revealed that the carbon fibers in the commingled and the prepreg composites were well covered with PEEK resin. While, in the cowoven cloth composites, the interfacial adhesion between the fiber and matrix was poor and then the fracture toughness was inferior to the other composites. The fracture surface of the commingled composite was rough and irregular and the carbon fibers were twisted. Therefore, the crack propagates the longer path, the more is the dissipated energy for the commingled composite. As a result, the fracture energies of the CF/PEEK composites obtained are in the order : commingled>prepreg>cowoven. The fracture toughness of the CF/epoxy composite was lower than that of CF/PEEK cowoven composite, because of the brittleness of the epoxy matrix.

REFERENCES

1. I. Y. Chang, *SAMPE Quart.*, **19** (4), 29(1988).
2. J. T. Hartness, *SAMPE J.*, Sep/Oct, 26(1984).
3. K. Friedrich, *et.al. J. Mater. Sci.*, **24**, 3387(1989).
4. A. J. Smiley and R. B. Pipes, *J. Compos. Mater.*, **21**, 670(1987).
5. Q. Wang and G. S. Springer, *J. Compos. Mater.*, **23**, 434(1989).
6. A. Lustiger, *J. Compos. Mater.*, **24**, 175(1990).
7. A. C. Handermann, *20th Int. SAMPE Tech. Conf.*, Sep.27-29, 681(1988).
8. K. Hukuda, *Kyoka Plastics*(in Japanese), **32** (4), 160(1986).
9. K.Takahashi and T.W. Chou, *Metall. Trans.*, **19A**, 129(1988).
10. K.Takahashi, *et. al., J. Japan Soc. Compos. Mater.*(in Japanese), **16**, 188(1990).

Fig.1 Plain weave cloth of commingled yarn and PEEK yarn.
warp : Commingled yarn (1800d) of carbon fiber with PEEK fiber
weft : PEEK yarn (70d)

Fig.2 Commingled yarn of fine carbon fiber with thick PEEK fiber.

Fig.3 A 5-shaft sateen cowoven cloth.
warp : carbon yarn(1800d)
weft : PEEK yarn (900d)

Fig.4 Geometry of the specimen used for the cleavage test.

Fig.5 Transverse stress-strain relations.

Fig.6 Transverse Young's modulus measured on : prepreg (○), commingled(△) and cowoven cloth(□) specimens.

Fig.7 Critical strain energy release rate, G_{IC} , vs. crack length \bar{a} .

Fig.8 Fracture surface of CF/PEEK prepreg composite.

(a)

(b)

Fig.9 Fracture surface of CF/PEEK commingled composite.

Fig.10 Fracture surface of CF/PEEK cowoven composite.

Fig.11 Fracture surface of CF/epoxy prepreg composite.